

Assessment of Knowledge of Triage and Its Barriers among Nurses working at Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

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Background: Triage is a critical process in emergency care that involves the timely and accurate identification of patients who require immediate treatment, distinguishing them from those whose conditions are less urgent and can safely wait for medical attention. Objectives: To measure the level of triage knowledge among emergency department nurses and to identify barriers that may affect triage knowledge and decision-making among emergency department nurses. Methodology: A cross sectional study was conducted at Indus Hospital Tando Muhammad Khan, a sample of 48 nurses was drawn using open epi software

through given population of 54 nurses, 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. Data was collected through structured questionnaire consisted of triage knowledge and its correlated factors. Data was analyzed through SPSS. Results: The majority of nurses

(54.2%) demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge. Additionally, 29.2% of participants showed a good level of knowledge, while 16.7% had poor knowledge. These results indicate that although a significant portion of nurses have moderate to good understanding of triage. Conclusion: Overall, the findings underscore the need for comprehensive strategies aimed at strengthening triage competencies among emergency nurses. These should include structured continuing education, the development and implementation of clear triage guidelines, and improvements in workplace conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Triage is a critical process in emergency care that involves the timely and accurate identification of patients who require immediate treatment, distinguishing them from those whose conditions are less urgent and can safely wait for medical attention (1). The quality of care provided in the ED has a significant impact not only on patient survival but also on overall hospital experience, care satisfaction, and psychological well-being (2). Nurses working in the Emergency Department (ED) are frontline healthcare providers responsible for the initial assessment and management of patients presenting with acute and potentially life-threatening conditions. The triage assessment, typically conducted by a triage nurse (TN), represents the first crucial interaction between the patient and the healthcare system. During this process, the TN must effectively evaluate the patient's clinical condition, determine the urgency of care required, and allocate medical resources according to established priority guidelines (3). However, discrepancies in triage decisions can occur. Under-triage involves missing critically ill patients whose conditions may deteriorate rapidly, whereas over-triage refers to prioritizing less severe cases, leading to the inefficient use of limited resources (4). In resource-constrained healthcare settings, the challenges faced by triage nurses are

intensified by factors such as overcrowding, high patient turnover, and limited staffing (5).

Because of the clinical nature of the ED, nurses are expected to possess skills, knowledge, and qualities that allow them to meet the high demands and expectations of patient care in this area(6).

In the studies conducted in other parts of the world, it has been established that the long waiting periods and patients' stay in the emergency ward are the results of inefficient workflow in the emergency departments due to lack of an effective triage unit to prioritize patients. Therefore, Correct and fast triage is the key to successful performance in an emergency ward, If not equipped with the necessary skills triage nurse can makes mistake in prioritizing patients(7).

Multiple studies worldwide have emphasized the critical role of nurses' triage knowledge in improving outcomes and saving lives in emergency situations. A study conducted in Jordan demonstrated that nurses with proper triage knowledge exhibited significantly better triage skills. It also found a strong positive correlation between triage skills and factors such as emergency department experience, previous triage experience, and completion of triage training courses (8). Similarly, research from Saudi Arabia revealed that while many nurses demonstrated a high level of triage knowledge and practice, there were still notable knowledge gaps and inconsistencies in applying that knowledge to real-life scenarios. The study recommended enhanced training and education in emergency nursing to address these deficiencies (9). In Pakistan, local studies have highlighted areas of concern. A study found that nurses had insufficient knowledge and skills related to triage, indicating a generally low level of preparedness (10). Another study conducted in Peshawar reported that a significant proportion of

nurses lacked formal triage training, which contributed to deficiencies in their knowledge. Importantly, the same study established that higher levels of triage knowledge were associated with greater accuracy in determining triage levels in the ED (11, 12).

Several factors affect the decision-making processes used by emergency nurses when performing triage. In previous studies, factors influencing the triage process were mainly studied with a focus on barriers, and they identified some of these barriers. For example, differences in nurse competency at the individual level were identified as barriers to be overcome (13). It was shown that these differences in emergency nurses' triage competency levels, which may result in deterioration in the accuracy of the triage, were caused by variations in their knowledge, assessment skill, experience, and education levels (14). The Emergency Nurse Association (ENA) in the United States and National Emergency Nurses Association (NENA) in Canada also emphasize that triage competence can be improved through a comprehensive, evidence-based triage education (15).

These findings collectively suggest that triage knowledge is closely linked to training, clinical experience, and educational background. Despite these insights, there is limited research in underrepresented regions of Pakistan, such as Tando Muhammad Khan.

RATIONAL

Understanding the level of triage knowledge and identifying factors associated with it among emergency department nurses is essential for improving education, policy-making, and clinical practice. By investigating these aspects, this study aims to provide

evidence-based insights that can support targeted interventions to enhance triage accuracy and efficiency in emergency settings.

OBJECTIVES

- To measure the level of triage knowledge among emergency department nurses.
- To identify barriers that may affect triage knowledge and decision-making among emergency department nurses.

METHODOLOGY

Study Setting: Indus Medical College (IMC) in Tando Muhammad Khan, Sindh, Pakistan, is a private medical institution established in 2011 by "Professional Associates (Pvt.) Ltd." according to Indus Medical College. It aims to provide quality medical education and produce competent doctors who can serve the community, both locally and internationally. The college is recognized by the Pakistan Medical & Dental Council (PMDC).

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: Indus Medical College Hospital, Tando Muhammad Khan.

Study Population: 54 Registered nurses working at hospital

Sample Size: A sample of 48 nurses was drawn from open epi software through following parameters:

Population: 54 nurses

Confidence Level: 95%

Margin of Error: 5%

Sampling Technique: Non probability purposive sampling is used.

Data Collection Tool: A structured, self-administered questionnaire is used, which will consist of two sections, section consist of demographic variables and section II consist of items asked regarding knowledge and barriers.

Data Analysis: Data was analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages) was used to summarize the data.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Approval is taken from the hospital administration. All nurses who take part in the study were given full information about the research. They asked to sign a consent form before filling out the questionnaire.

RESULTS

TABLE NO.01: AGE OF PARTICIPANT

		Frequency (n)	Percent
AGE	20-25	23	47.9%
	26-30	16	33.3%
	31-35	9	18.8%
	Total	48	100.0%

This table shows the age distribution of the participants in the study. The majority of the participants (47.9%) were in the 20–25 years age group, followed by 33.3% in the 26–30 years group. A smaller portion, 18.8%, were aged 31–35 years. This indicates that most emergency department nurses who participated in the study are relatively young, with nearly half being under the age of 26.

TABLE NO.02: GENDER OF PARTICIPANT

		Frequency (n)	Percent
Gender	Female	24	50.0%

Male	24	50.0%
Total	48	100.0%

This table presents the gender distribution of the study participants. Out of 48 participants, 50% were female and 50% were male, indicating an equal representation of both genders in the study. This balanced distribution helps minimize gender bias in the findings related to triage knowledge and associated factors.

TABLE NO.03: EDUCATION OF PARTICIPANT

		Frequency (n)	Percent
Valid	Diploma	11	22.9%
	BSN	28	58.3%
	MSN	9	18.8%
	Total	48	100.0%

This table illustrates the educational qualifications of the participants. The majority of the nurses, 58.3%, held a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree, followed by 22.9% with a Diploma in Nursing, and 18.8% with a Master of Science in Nursing (MSN). This suggests that most participants had at least a bachelor's level education, indicating a well-qualified nursing workforce in the emergency department.

TABLE NO.04: OVERALL KNOWLEDGE

	Frequency	Percent
Poor	8	16.7%
Moderate	26	54.2%
Good	14	29.2%
Total	48	100.0

This table displays the overall level of triage knowledge among the participants. The majority of nurses (54.2%) demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge. Additionally, 29.2% of participants showed a good level of knowledge, while 16.7% had poor knowledge. These results indicate that although a significant portion of nurses have moderate to good understanding of triage, there is still a notable percentage with poor knowledge, highlighting the need for continued education and training programs.

TABLE NO.05: WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING DO YOU CONSIDER THE MAIN BARRIER TO IMPROVING YOUR KNOWLEDGE OF TRIAGE IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT?

Barriers	Frequency	Percent
Lack of formal education	16	33.3%
Heavy workload	15	31.3%
Absence of triage protocols	11	22.9%
Limited hands-on or practical experience with triage	3	6.3%
Poor communication and coordination within team	3	6.3%
Total	48	100.0%

This table highlights the participants' views on the main barriers to enhancing their triage knowledge in the emergency department. The most frequently reported barrier was lack of formal education, cited by 33.3% of the nurses. This was followed closely by heavy workload (31.3%), and absence of triage protocols (22.9%). A smaller proportion of participants identified limited hands-on experience (6.3%) and poor communication and coordination within the emergency team (6.3%) as barriers. These findings suggest that educational gaps and systemic workload issues are the primary challenges affecting nurses' ability to improve their triage knowledge.

DISCUSSION

The current study assessed the knowledge of triage and its associated factors among emergency department nurses. The demographic findings show that nearly half of the participants (47.9%) were aged between 20 and 25 years, suggesting that the majority of emergency nurses were relatively young. This may be due to increasing recruitment of fresh graduates in emergency departments, which has been similarly observed in studies from other developing healthcare settings where younger nurses constitute a significant portion of the workforce due to rapid turnover and staffing shortages (16, 17).

An equal gender distribution (50% male, 50% female) was observed, reflecting a balanced representation. This is an encouraging sign of gender equity in nursing roles within emergency settings, where traditionally, females have been more dominant. Recent studies emphasize that a diverse workforce can enhance team dynamics and patient care outcomes in high-stress environments like emergency departments (18, 19). With respect to educational qualifications, a significant proportion of nurses held a BSN degree (58.3%), followed by diploma holders (22.9%) and MSN-qualified nurses (18.8%). These findings are consistent with national trends in nursing education, where the educational background and continuous training directly impact on knowledge levels, bachelor's-level education is increasingly becoming the standard entry-level qualification for professional nursing practice (1). Studies show that higher educational levels among nurses are associated with better clinical decision-making and patient outcomes, especially in complex care areas such as triage (20, 21). Regarding triage knowledge, more than half of the nurses (54.2%) demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge, while 29.2% showed good knowledge and 16.7% had poor knowledge. These results are similar to those reported by Alquraini et al. (2021), who found that

many emergency nurses have a foundational understanding of triage but lack depth in critical areas (19). This emphasizes the need for targeted training and continuing education programs to enhance nurses' confidence and accuracy in triage decision-making (22,23).

When asked about barriers to improving triage knowledge, 33.3% of participants cited lack of formal education as the primary obstacle, followed by heavy workload (31.3%) and absence of triage protocols (22.9%). These findings align with a study which stated that the burnout among nurses can also vary depending on the department they work in. Nurses working in the emergency department are even more susceptible to burnout due to factors such as high workload, long shifts, inadequate staffing, constant contact with critically ill patients, exposure to mortality, and more interaction with patient companions compared to other departments(9). Moreover, workload-related stress and lack of institutional support have been identified as persistent barriers that compromise the effectiveness of triage in emergency departments (24, 25). Findings from many studies suggest that many gaps in triage knowledge among emergency department nurses are found as barriers. While the majority possesses at least a moderate understanding, institutional factors such as training deficiencies and resource limitations significantly hinder their ability to enhance this knowledge. These insights support the need for structured educational interventions, updated protocols, and supportive working environments to optimize triage practices (26, 27, 28).

CONCLUSION

In terms of triage knowledge, while most nurses demonstrated a moderate understanding, a significant number still showed poor knowledge, indicating the presence of knowledge gaps that could impact clinical outcomes in emergency settings.

The study also identified key barriers to enhancing triage knowledge, including lack of formal training, heavy workload, and absence of standardized triage protocols. These challenges are consistent with broader literature pointing to systemic issues such as burnout, staffing shortages, and inadequate institutional support.

Overall, the findings underscore the need for comprehensive strategies aimed at strengthening triage competencies among emergency nurses. These should include structured continuing education, the development and implementation of clear triage guidelines, and improvements in workplace conditions. By addressing these barriers, healthcare institutions can enhance both the efficiency and accuracy of triage processes, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes in emergency departments.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Hospitals and healthcare institutions should organize periodic in-service training and workshops focused on triage protocols, decision-making, and prioritization of care. These programs should be evidence-based and tailored to the specific challenges of emergency settings.
- Nursing education institutions should integrate comprehensive triage training into undergraduate and postgraduate curricula, ensuring that nurses enter the workforce with adequate theoretical and practical knowledge.
- Institutions must ensure that updated, standardized triage protocols are available and accessible in all emergency departments. These protocols should be aligned with international best practices and adapted to local healthcare needs.
- To mitigate burnout and ensure optimal triage performance, hospital administrations should assess staffing needs and allocate sufficient human

resources in emergency departments. This will allow nurses to carry out triage duties more effectively without compromising patient care.

- Nurses should be encouraged and supported to participate in Continuing Professional Development CPD activities related to emergency care and triage. Offering incentives or linking CPD to career progression may improve participation.

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